

The Effect of Cash Conversion Cycle on Profitability of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises.

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Abstract

Working capital management holds an important place among financial management decisions. Firms' keeping working capital continuously in the long term depends on investments on working capital. The optimal level of working capital for a firm can be provided when there is a balance between profitability and liquidity. The aim of this study is to examine the effect of cash conversion cycle which is used to evaluate the effectiveness of working capital management on profitability of firms. With this aim, data set between 2009 and 2013 from 19 firms in Gümüşhane city in Turkey working in the fields of fruit leather and churchkhela production have been used. According to the results of panel data analysis results, there is a positive effect of cash conversion cycle on profitability of firms.

Keywords: Working Capital Management, Profitability, Cash Conversion Cycle, Panel Data Analysis

Introduction

Financial management is divided into three major fields, namely capital budgeting, capital structure and working capital. However, it is notable that when the literature is reviewed there is more interest in capital budgeting and capital structure and not enough interest in working capital management. In other words, there are many studies on long-term decision making while studies on short-term decision making are limited in finance literature. In fact, working capital is the extent of power to pay short-term debts and the ability to fulfill urgent needs. So, working capital

Investment decisions are one of the most discussed topics in the finance literature. When studies on this topic are examined, it is seen that researchers generally focus on long-term financial decisions such as capital structure, profit distribution and company valuation. However, investments on circulating assets in short-term have an important part in total assets for both small and big (Hawawini et al., 1986).

Working capital fulfills short-term financial needs of enterprises and represents a financial capital. Stocks that are an important part of working capital reduce the cost of problems that might be faced in the production process and of not being able to meet demand growth and protects the enterprise against fluctuations (Blinder and Manccini, 1991). Besides, commercial claims promotes product's being bought especially when the demand level is low (Emery, 1987), helps consumers' being persuaded about the amount and quality of the product before paying and

and its management is very important for enterprises. Working capital management includes the level of investment to circulating assets which is the important part of total asset investments and the decisions related to financing these investments. An effective working capital management requires balancing the risk and profitability appropriately, removing risks that might come up while the enterprise tries to perform short-term responsibilities, planning and controlling temporary investments and liabilities well in order to prevent over investment on temporary investment components.

enterprises' forming long-term relations with their (Ng et al., 1999).

Working capital management has important effects on company profitability and risk so on firm value (Smith, 1980). An effective working capital management requires removing risks that might come up while the enterprise tries to perform short-term responsibilities, planning and controlling temporary investments and liabilities well in order to prevent over investment on temporary investment components (Eljelly, 2004).

In this context, working capital which is firms' short-term investments has an important effect on total assets and firm profitability.

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of working capital management on the profitability of firms. With this aim, the effect of cash conversion cycle (CCC) management which consists of firms' accounts receivable turnover, accounts payable turnover, stock turnover and net

trade time on firm profitability has been examined through the data from 19 firms working in the fields of fruit leather and churchkhela production in Gümüşhane city of Turkey.

1. Literature

While there are many studies that research for the effect of working capital management on the firms' profitability and operations, most of them use ratios like liquidity and activity that measure the operation effectiveness of the firm in order to evaluate the effectiveness of working capital management. However, Gitman who thought that using liquidity ratios in measure of effectiveness was not enough used CCC for the first time to measure the effect of working capital management on profitability in his research in 1974 (Silva; 2011).

In his research that examines firm profitability by CCC, Soenen (1993) points out an important relation with American firms' CCC and investment profitability. Similarly, in their study in which they examine American firms, Fazzari and Petersen (1993) put forth that working capital management components are affected three times more than other variables in recession.

In the study by Önal (1996), the importance of cash management for the enterprises is emphasized. In the end of the study, it is stated that cash management turns into an operation that firms aim to get interest income by using cash surplus in financial instruments.

In their study in which they use the data between 1995 and 2000 from 167 enterprises whose shares are publicly traded in İMKB, Yücel and Kurt (2002) examine CCC, profitability, liquidity and debt structure comparing towards sectors and firm scales. According to findings, there is a positive relation between CCC and liquidity ratios while there is a negative relation between CCC and return on assets and equity capital.

Pointing out the importance of working capital management, Eljelly (2004) states that an effective liquidity management which consists of planning and controlling of current assets prevents the risk of not being able to fulfill short-term responsibilities and over-inverting on these assets. In the study, the relation between profitability and

liquidity for Saudi Arabian companies has been examined through correlation and regression analysis and CCC has been found to be a more important measurement than current ratio on effect of firm profitability.

Şamiloğlu and Demirgüneş (2008), perform a cross sectional regression analysis on financial tables of production companies whose shares were publicly traded in İMKB between 1998 and 2007 and find out an important negative relation between CCC, ADS, SDS and profitability.

In the study by Luo et al. (2009), data from firms working in production, wholesale and retail sectors and whose shares were publicly traded in Compustat between 1980 and 2006 were used. Return on assets (ROA) was used as dependent variable and the effect of CCC, sales, size, asset turnover and profit margin on ROA has been measured. In that study, it is pointed out that first of all a successful and effective working capital management increases the firm value in the eye of shareholders.

Ramachandran and Janakiraman (2009) search for the relation between working capital management and earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) in Indian paper sector. According to the results of this study that use a 10 year period data, there is a negative relation between CCC and EBIT.

Uyar (2009) who performs correlation analysis to one year data from 164 firms whose shares are publicly traded in İMKB finds out a negative relation between CCC and both profitability and firm scale.

Şen and Oruç (2009) examine the relation between CCC and its components with profitability through general sample and forming a different model for each sector and find a negative sided relation between CCC and accounts receivable turnover and stock turnover and a positive sided relation between CCC and profitability in all sectors except textile.

In their study in which they used the data from 52 production firms whose shares publicly traded in İMKB between 2000 and 2010, Meder and Çakır (2013) reveal that firms can increase their profitability by increasing their CCC.

Muscettola (2014) points out a positive sided

relation between debt collection period which is one of the important components of CCC and profitability in the study on production firms in Italy.

2. Application

Small and medium scale enterprises (SMSEs) which is important for national economies are supported in both developed and developing countries and detailed studies are carried out on the topic. On the other hand, SMSEs' financial structure's being powerful is a requirement for the success of mentioned supports and efforts. SMSEs -depending on their financial structure, production volume and capital structure- face different problems than big scale enterprises. Such enterprises have difficulty in receiving credits from banks since their equity capital and capital structure are not sufficient and demand of powerful assurance by credit institutions like banks. According to Canbaş (1998), SMSEs face mostly the problem of not being able to collateralize in the way of financing through credit and when they apply to banks for credit to meet their short-term financial needs they cannot fulfill the condition of hypothec or warranty asked by the banks to credit. Besides, researches by OECD show that SMSEs are affected more from resource cost and financial insufficiency than large scale firms.

How CCC which is one of the most important components of working capital in SMSEs affect profitability is an important detail. In this context, the aim of the study is to find out how CCC of SMSEs in Gümüşhane affect their profitability. The sample includes 19 SMSEs working in the fields of fruit leather and churchkhela production in Gümüşhane city.

2.1. Method and Data Set

In the study, models that are formed in order to determine the effect of working capital

management on firm profitability are estimated through panel data analysis. Panel data analysis is a kind of analyze depending on estimating financial relations by using section datum of a time dimension (Greene, 1997). This analysis depends on repetitive variance and variance models as observations within the section are repeated through the years (Pazarlıoğlu, 2001). The use of horizontal section and time series analysis together provides more flexibility to the analyzer than the use of mentioned analysis separately by increasing the quality and quantity of data (Gujarati, 2003).

Data set between 2009 and 2013 from 19 firms working in the fields of fruit leather and churchkhela production in Gümüşhane city has been used.

2.2. Model and Variables

The model used in the study is as follows after control variables are added:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 CCC + \beta_2 FL - \beta_3 CGS + \beta_4 TAT + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In this model, abbreviations represent; ROA return on assets, CCC cash conversion cycle, FL financial leverage, CGS cost of goods sold and TAT total asset turnover.

Return on assets is an important variable that is used to measure profitability in firms (DeLoof, 2003, p.576) so ROE is used as dependent variable in the study. CCC which is used as independent variable is one of the major variables used in measuring the effectiveness of working capital management. In addition, asset turnover, financial leverage and sold product cost are in the model as control variable.

How variables used in the model are calculated is shown in Table-1.

Table 1: Variables Used in the Model

Variable	KISALTMA	Calculation
Dependent Variable	ROA	Net Profit Average / Total Assets
	TAT	Net Sales / Total Assets
Independent Variables	FL	Short Term Debt + Long Term Debt / Total Equity
	CGS	Cost of Goods Sold
	CCC	Accounts Receivable Collection Period + Average Inventory Investment Period – Debt Payment Period

Similar studies that use the variables in the model and their results are summarized in Table-2.

Table 2. Similar Studies on CCC

AUTHORS	YEAR	SAMPLE	DATA SET	ANALYSIS	RESULTS
Soenen	1993	USA Companies	1985-1990	Regression Analysis	There is a relationship between CCC and return on investment.
Fazzari and Petersen	1993	USA Companies	1975-1982	Comparative Analysis	Working capital is three times more changeable than investments in non-current assets in recession periods.
Weinraub and Visscher	1998	USA Companies	1984-1993	Comparative Analysis	Meaningfully <i>different</i> working capital management policies are applied in sectors.
Opler et al.	1999	USA Companies	1974-1994	Frequency Distributions and Cross Sectional Analysis	Firms whose cash flow is under risk prefer keeping cash instead of assets that will provide cash inflow.
Lazaridis and Tryfonidis	2006	Athens Stock Exchange	2001-2004	Regression Analysis	There is a negative relation between profitability and CCC.
Rehman	2006	Islamabad Stock Exchange	1999-2004	Regression Analysis	There is a strong and negative sided relationship between working capital ratios and firm profitability.
Öz and Güngör	2007	Stock Exchange of İstanbul	1992-2005	Panel Data Analysis	There is a negative relationship between accounts receivable turnover, accounts payable turnover, stock turnover, net trade time which represent working capital management and firm profitability.
Appuhami	2008	Tayland Stock Exchange	2000-2005	Panel Data Analysis	Capital expenditures has an effect on working capital.
Gill, et al.	2010	New York Stock Exchange	2005-2007	Panel Data Analysis	There is statistically significant relationship between CCC and profitability.
Meder Çakır	2013	Stock Exchange of İstanbul	2000-2010	Panel Data Analysis	CCC affects profitability positively.
Anser and Malik	2013	Islamabad Exchange	2007-2011	Panel Data Analysis	CCC is having significantly inverse association with both return on assets and equity.
Muscettola	2014	Italian manufacturing SMEs	2007-2010	Regression Analysis	There is positive relationship between Accounts Receivable Turnover and profitability.

2.3. Findings Related to Model Study

Descriptive statistics related to data used in the

model are given in Table-3 and correlation matrix among variables is given in Table-4.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
ROA	95	0,154378	0,01577346	0,00476	0,9978595
CCC	95	126,7947	134.6376	0.62	453.6
FL	95	1,58937	2,407052	0,12	11,28926
CGS	95	1.263.727	4076646	4595	3.360.350
TAT	95	1,769956	1,624662	1,2124	8,667542

When Table-3 is examined, the mean of return on assets of the firms in the study is about 15%. On the other hand, the mean of asset turnover is low

as 1,769956. This situations shows that firms do not use their assets effectively.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix among the Variables

	ROA	CCC	FL	CGS	TAT
ROA	1.0000				
CCC	0.3526	1.0000			
FL	0.0472	-0.2225	1.0000		
CGS	-0.2282	0.5147	0.0966	1.0000	
TAT	0.0242	-0.4024	0.1007	-0.1992	1.0000

When Table-4 is examined, it is seen that there is negative relationship between ROA and CGS while there is a positive relation between ROA and other variables. Besides, there is a negative relationship between FL and CCC, TAT and CCC and TAT and CGS.

Unit root tests were performed for each variable in order to find out if series are fixed. When panel unit root tests were examined, the p values were seen to be less than 0.05 which means there is not general unit root within the series.

Hausman test was used in order to decide to use

whether fixed effects model or random effects model in the study. Hausman test that adapts Chi-square distribution with k freedom degree is used to choose between fixed effects model and random effects model (Baltagi, 2001: 20). Random effects model was chosen and interpreted since Hausman test result's p value was lower than 0.05 ((H0: $E(\varepsilon_{it} | X_{it}) = 0$ section data and time series effects are random, there is no correlation).

Analysis results of the model used in the study is given in Table-5.

Table 5: Model Analysis Results

Model : $ROA_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 CCC + \beta_2 FL - \beta_3 CGS + \beta_4 TAT + \varepsilon_{it}$				
Dependent Variable: ROA		$R^2 = 0.1923$		
Periods: 2009 - 2013		Wald $\chi^2 = 14.07$		
		Prob > F = 0.0074		
Independent Variable	Coefficient	Std. Err.	t	P
CCC	0.0352833	0.0119234	2.96	0.002*
FL	0.0102093	0.0069113	1.48	0.145
CGS	-0.000188	0.0003965	-2.98	0.003*
TAT	0.0003763	0.0001965	1.92	0.037*

*5% significant

As seen in Table-5, since p value (0.0074) related to F value which tests significance level of

presented equation is lower than 0.05, formed model is seen to be significant in 95% reliability

level. The explanation level of ROA by the variables used in the model is 19% ($R^2 = 0.1923$).

When the model was applied, it was seen that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship at the level of 5% between CCC and ROA. There are studies in the literature that point out either positive or negative relationship between CCC and ROA (Table-2). Similarly, a relationship that is positive and statistically meaningful at the level of 5% was found between TAT and ROA. On the other hand, there is a negative sided and statistically significant relationship at the level of 5% between CGS and ROA. In other words, increase of CGS affects firm's profitability negatively. That is an expected result which is seen in the literature.

Conclusion

Working capital management in SMSEs takes much time of firm managers. This situation creates a big pressure on managers' decisions and causes wrong decisions. Firm managers should follow the sector, customers and suppliers closely as well as their own firm in order make right decisions because an increase or decrease in maturity dates effects firms differently. CCC that is consisted of debt collection, stock turnover and debt discharging periods is one of the important components of working capital. So, the effect of CCC on firms' profitability has been the topic of many researches.

In the study, the effect of CCC on firms' profitability has been examined and data set between 2009 and 2013 from 19 firms working in the fields of fruit leather and churchkhela production in Gümüşhane city has been used. Formed model reveals that CCC has a positive relation with ROA that is accepted as dependent variable. This can be interpreted as SMSEs keep their CCC low and this affects firm profitability negatively. Increase in maturity dates will increase firms' sales which in turn will increase their profits. However, increase in maturity dates will increase their loses that is described bad debts also. Firm managers should analyze costs of investments to debts and stocks and profit rates as the results of these costs well while increasing CCCs. Otherwise, increase of CCC will make firms face cash flow problem and financial cost caused by it.

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